

STUDY OF FACTORS AFFECTING REAL ESTATE VALUATION

Kakhramanova Jansaya

Tashkent architecture-construction university graduate student

Annotation . When determining the market value of real estate, it is necessary to take into account several important factors, such as the location of the object, the region, the land area of the object, the date of commissioning of the object, the purpose of the object, the level of physical and mental wear and tear. This article is about this.

Key words: real estate, evaluation, space planning, architecture, construction, utilities, ecology, local factors, natural resources.

Introduction.

The change in the value of any property depends on a number of factors that appear at different stages of the evaluation process, these factors can be assigned to three different hierarchical levels.

The first level (regional) is the influence of factors of a general nature that are not related to a specific property and are not directly related to it, but indirectly affect the processes that occur with real estate in the market. the level of mystery and therefore the property is appreciated.

The second level (local) is the level of influence of local factors, mainly on the scale of a city or urban area. These factors are directly related to the analysis of the object being evaluated and similar real estate objects and operations on them.

The third level (immediate environment) is the level of influence of factors related to the property and largely dependent on its characteristics.

Main part.

The influence of factors can occur simultaneously at different levels and can be taken into account sequentially depending on the detailed level of assessment and the type of value being assessed. The real estate appraiser must determine the impact of

each factor on the final price, then the impact of all factors in total, and make a general conclusion about the value of the property, supported by the necessary grounds.

The first level includes the following 4 groups of factors:

- social:

- basic needs for purchasing real estate, in the option of their use; basic needs for communication with others, attitude to neighboring objects and their owners, sense of ownership;

- trends in the population change, its rejuvenation or aging, the number of families, population density, etc.;

- trends in the level of education, the level of culture, and the level of crime;

- lifestyle and level.

- economic:

- the general state of the world economy; economic situation at the country, region, local level; financial status of enterprises;

- demand factors: level of employment, level of income and trends in its change, solvency, availability of credit resources, interest rates and rent, costs of forming sales, providing the population with communal facilities, etc.;

- supply factors: availability of financing sources and conditions for construction and reconstruction, number of objects for sale; costs of construction and assembly work and their trend, taxes.

- physical:

- climatic conditions, natural resources and sources of raw materials, relief, soil, etc.;

- ecology;

- seismic factors.

- political (administrative):

- political stability, security;

- tax policy, financial policy, giving various benefits;

- zoning: prohibitive, restrictive or liberal;
- construction norms and rules: restrictive or liberal;
- public utility services: roads, landscaping, engineering equipment, public transport, schools, fire service;
- the existence and improvement of legislation (on mortgages, on property, on transactions related to real estate, in the field of ecology, on collateral, in the field of construction, credit policy on etc.), real estate and appraisal activity licensing.

The second level includes the following factors:

- Address:
 - in relation to the business center, workplaces, residential areas, highways, railways, coasts, green areas, communal services (waste dumps, etc.);
 - availability and status of means of communication;
 - existence of socio-cultural objects;
 - placement of objects in the city (district), neighborhood environmental plan.
- terms of sale:
 - special conditions of operations; motives of sellers and buyers
 - financing conditions: lending conditions; interest rates; conditions of appropriation of funds.

The third level includes the following factors:

- physical characteristics:
 - physical indicators: area, dimensions, shape, construction material, year of construction or reconstruction, number of floors, etc.;
 - quality of construction and use;
 - availability of communal services;
 - functional suitability;
 - attractiveness, convenience.
- architecture and construction:
 - style, location, construction, etc.;

- space planning indicators, etc.
- financial and operational:
 - operating expenses;
 - construction cost;
 - income from property.

Summary:

The service life of a building varies, and this is an important factor related to when the building was built and what construction materials were used. Checking this requires the use of a number of modern tools and equipment. Depending on the size of the facility, it is more important to check its remaining service life. We know that reconstruction or capital repair of buildings and structures requires a lot of money. Regardless of the purpose, the remaining service life of the building we are buying should be in line with our plans.

List of used literature:

1. Friedman J, Ordway Nick. Analyzing and evaluating income-generating real estate. From Peruvian English. - M.: Delo, 1997. - 480 p. – ISBN 5-7749-0045-2
2. Turdiev, AS, Kakhramonov, KS, & Yusupdjanova, NU (2020). Digital economy: experience of foreign countries and features of development in Uzbekistan. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 04 (84), 660-664.
3. Elina Kunaeva, financial director of Namuna Development. (real estate, year-end) information
4. Toychiyev NJ, Mirhoshimov AM, Plakhtiy KA Fundamentals of Real Estate Appraisal. Study guide. - T.: "Adolat", 2000, - 148b.
5. Shoha'zami Sh.Sh. Property theory, value and price.-T.: Fanvatechnologiya, 2012. - 264 p.